

A. N. Timokhovich

Peculiarities of consumer behavior in the segment of the restaurant business (using the example of Moscow establishments)

KEYWORDS

restaurant business,
consumer behavior,
macro environment factors,
restaurant trends,
digital technologies,
audience involvement

ABSTRACT

Introduction. The relevance of studying consumer behavior characteristics in the restaurant business segment stems from economic factors, including the population's income level and inflation, which impact consumer behavior in the restaurant industry.

This study aims to identify the peculiarities of the restaurant market and consumer behavior in the Moscow restaurant services market.

Materials and methods. The research materials consisted of scientific articles, books, and publications on consumer behavior in the restaurant business and marketing strategies in this area.

Results. Within the framework of the study, three stages were implemented. At the first stage, an analysis of the macroenvironment of the Moscow restaurant market was conducted to identify external factors influencing the modern restaurant business. External factors that have both positive and negative impacts on the development of the restaurant industry were structured and described. At the second stage, to identify the main trends in the Moscow restaurant market, a content analysis method was used to examine the websites of Moscow restaurant business establishments with high rating indicators, based on data from the Yandex neural network. The main trends in the Moscow restaurant market include the orientation of restaurants towards preparing healthy meals and vegetarian cuisine, the use of farm products and local ingredients in prepared dishes, the introduction of technological innovations that simplify the consumer experience, a focus on sustainability in the business model, and a variety of restaurant formats. At the third stage of the study, a survey was conducted among visitors to restaurants and cafes in Moscow to identify the characteristics of their consumer behavior. The identified consumer practices in the restaurant market indicate, on the one hand, the active involvement of the audience in visiting restaurants, cafes, and bars in Moscow; on the other hand, the use of restaurant delivery services through restaurant websites or mobile applications. The dominant influence of rational factors was revealed when consumers choose a restaurant to visit, changing the structure of consumer motivation when visiting restaurants and cafes.

Conclusion. As areas of further research corresponding to the subject area, we designate: the study of changes in consumer practices under the influence of the VUCA environment; exploring the impact of digital and standard communication tools on restaurant decision-making; and examining the phenomenon of customers visiting restaurant establishments on a budget.

FOR CITATION

Received: Dec 5, 2023
Accepted: Feb 21, 2024
Published: Jun 1, 2024

Timokhovich, A. N. (2024). Peculiarities of consumer behavior in the segment of the restaurant business (using the example of Moscow establishments). *Economic Consultant*, (2), 74–87. <https://doi.org/10.46224/ecoc.2024.2.6>

This is an open access article distributed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike International License (CC-BY-SA 4.0) that allows others to share the work with an acknowledgement of the work's authorship and initial publication in this journal

INTRODUCTION

The relevance of studying consumer behavior characteristics in the restaurant business segment stems from economic factors, including the population's income level and inflation, which impact consumer behavior in the restaurant industry. It is also worth noting that consumer tastes and preferences are constantly evolving in response to changing cultural, social, and economic factors. Understanding these changes enables restaurateurs to tailor their offerings and remain competitive. The introduction of digital technologies (mobile applications and online food delivery services) allows you to optimize marketing strategies and improve your customer experience.

The Moscow restaurant market is diverse and dynamically developing. Despite the challenges of recent years (the pandemic, withdrawal from the foreign restaurant market, and sanctions restrictions), the restaurant market has recovered and rebounded. On the Moscow market, restaurants are offering a wide range of national cuisines, from classic Russian establishments to Japanese sushi bars and Italian pizzerias. The formats of the establishments are also diverse, ranging from street cafes to Michelin-rated restaurants.

The Moscow restaurant market boasts a rich history, dating back to the opening of the first restaurants in the 19th century. Then, restaurants offered their guests traditional Russian dishes, such as pancakes and borscht. After the October Revolution of 1917, many private restaurants were nationalized, and the restaurant market began to be regulated by the state. Soviet citizens dined in canteens and cafes, which offered relatively affordable prices and standardized dishes [1].

During the collapse of the Soviet Union, the Moscow restaurant market underwent significant changes, becoming more differentiated. Foreign restaurants and cafes offering international cuisine were opened in the city. The development of business restaurants and places with entertainment programs also characterizes the post-Soviet period.

In 2024, 21,600 catering establishments were operating in Moscow [2].

According to analytical studies, revenue growth in Moscow cafes, restaurants, and bars for 2023 reached 16%, totaling 550 billion rubles [3]. The attendance of restaurant business institutions in Moscow in 2023 increased by 18% compared to the previous year; the average check increased by 44 rubles and amounted to 703 rubles [4].

In comparison with other regions of Russia, the Moscow restaurant market is not only the most profitable but also highly competitive [5]. Due to the existing diversity, restaurants compete for the attention and loyalty of consumers; therefore, along with high-quality and tasty dishes, qualified staff, and an attractive atmosphere, each successful business utilizes its marketing strategy to promote itself [6].

The Moscow restaurant market continues to develop, responding to shifting consumer preferences and emerging trends.

One of the key success factors for establishments in the Moscow restaurant market is the adoption of new technologies and online services. Many restaurants offer their services through mobile applications, while also introducing internet marketing and social media promotion tools to attract new customers and retain loyal ones [7].

The study of the peculiarities of the restaurant market and consumer behavior among restaurant and cafe visitors is relevant.

The purpose of this study is to identify the peculiarities of the restaurant market and consumer behavior in the Moscow restaurant services market.

Object of research: Moscow restaurants and cafes; consumers of Moscow restaurants and cafes.

Subject of research: features of the restaurant market and consumer behavior of visitors to Moscow restaurants and cafes.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study design includes three main stages: conducting a PEST analysis to identify external influences on the modern restaurant business; content analysis of websites of Moscow restaurant business establishments to identify the main trends in the Moscow restaurant market; surveying visitors and consumers of the Moscow restaurant market to identify the characteristics of consumer behavior in the restaurant services market.

The research materials were scientific articles, books and publications on consumer behavior in the restaurant business and marketing strategies in this area (Quality & Quantity, Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies, Electronic Markets, Electronic Commerce Research, Humanities and Social Sciences Communications, Eurasian Studies in Business and Economics, International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity, etc.).

LITEATURE REVIEW

A. Rejeb et al. finds that research related to the restaurant business primarily focuses on five thematic groups: consumer behavior, consumer satisfaction, social networks, green restaurants, and authenticity. At the same time, consumer behavior was the main topic; however, the focus of this area of research recently shifted from traditional to luxury and ethnic restaurants. The authors also identify a shift in publication as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic [8].

P. Mohanty et al. write that measures such as lockdowns and social distancing were necessary during the COVID-19 pandemic. Still, they had a detrimental impact on businesses, particularly those focused mainly on face-to-face communication, such as the restaurant and catering industries. On the other hand, the surge in technological advances has become a “lifeline” for the restaurant industry [9].

P. Karthikeyan et al. believe that having a broad online presence is essential for any restaurant to achieve real success and prosperity [10].

J. Boabaid & S. Marnoto consider the specifics of using food delivery apps by restaurants. According to the authors, these tools represent a new channel for restaurants and can be viewed as a means to increase sales. At the same time, restaurant managers themselves acknowledge the loss of control over sales in restaurants, changes in customer behavior and expectations, and the difficulty in managing and retaining customers [11].

A. J. Steur et al., using the restaurant booking platform as an example, study the impact of reviews on the duration of consumer purchase decisions. The authors believe that contradictory reviews lead to a longer time required for making decisions about buying in a restaurant [12].

E. Fairshstein writes that delivery menus, the ability to order through aggregators, and delivery times are significant factors in positive restaurant reviews. All three of these factors are related to service logistics [13].

K. S. Zhang et al. write that with the development of the Internet, an increasing number of consumers can access various information and book restaurant reservations through integrated platforms. The authors demonstrate that the higher the cognitive risk associated with consumers, the greater their willingness to use the online booking system [14]. The cognitive risk to consumers is their uncertainty and the potential negative consequences they foresee when making a purchase or engaging in a particular activity.

S. Banerjee et al. believe that fast food restaurants (QSRs) experimenting with menus and introducing new ordering and delivery methods are improving their sales. The authors demonstrate that social networks can also be utilized to enhance market positions locally [15].

G. Fauza et al. developed twenty-five attributes, drawn from the food safety practice literature for the restaurant, to assess food quality, service quality, and restaurant environment and facilities. Based on a survey of 153 respondents, the authors conclude that it is necessary to improve restaurant premises and food quality [16].

E. S. W. Ling et al. provide data from an online survey conducted among customers of dessert cafe chains in Malaysia. The authors concluded that the characteristic of “innovativeness” evokes positive emotions in clients and improves their social image [17].

G. Kankam examines the impact of innovation on the quality of service, leading to business efficiency. According to the author, innovation fully mediates the relationship between the quality of service and business efficiency among restaurants in Ghana [18].

The regional features of the restaurant business, namely, cultural, economic, social, and geographical conditions, are not to be neglected either. In particular, according to T. Kholod et al., Italy, which has a long tradition of eating out, experienced a slower transition to delivery compared to other countries [19]. R. Akamatsu et al. highlight Japan’s national goals of minimizing food waste and promoting a healthy weight [20]. Overconsumption is one of the most significant public health challenges in the UK, and it is linked to the rising consumption of food ordered through delivery platforms [21].

Therefore, it is necessary to analyze further existing theories and models of consumer behavior, as well as their adaptation to the specific needs of the restaurant industry. To understand the characteristics of consumer behavior, it is essential to conduct empirical research and collect and analyze data on consumer preferences, motivations, and behaviors. The results of research in the field of consumer behavior can contribute to the development of marketing theory and management in the restaurant industry, as well as offer practical recommendations for enhancing business operations.

RESULTS

Analysis of the Moscow restaurant market macro environment

At the first stage of the study, the macroenvironment of the Moscow restaurant market was analyzed using a PEST analysis to identify external factors affecting the

modern restaurant business. PEST is a business evaluation tool used to determine how external factors can impact a company's operations. PEST analysis can also be used as part of strategic planning to optimize current conditions, forecast future developments, and prepare for immediate changes to strengthen the business and remain competitive.

As political factors, we will designate the following: a tense political situation affects international relations, which involves the determination of the price, cost of food production; the political situation affects the development of domestic tourism (change in the composition of guests); an increase in import substitution is recorded under sanctions restrictions; laws on how the restaurant should work come into force (quality and safety of products, licenses, sanitization, medical examination of employees, technical regulation, etc.).

Economic factors are: rising inflation; falling disposable incomes of Russians; rising demand for full-service restaurants; increase in the cost of raw materials and equipment due to the increase in the price of currency; an increase in domestic tourism flows (an increase in demand for visiting restaurants and cafes in tourist places); financial support by the state of the business sector, in particular, support for the Moscow restaurant business through grants, subsidies, concessional lending; high competition in the Moscow restaurant market.

The main socio-demographic factors are: a shift in demand from fast food to organic, healthy food; the impact of the pandemic on consumer choice in favor of delivering restaurant meals instead of visiting an establishment; the phenomenon of "seizing stress" as a reason for a sharp increase in the volume of the restaurant market, the number of visits and an increase in the average check in 2022-2023; difficulties with international travel – Russians have become more likely to choose domestic tourism for recreation, which leads to an increase in the need to visit restaurants; high population density in Moscow, which contributes to the demand for restaurant business services; labor migration processes that are actively represented in the metropolitan area.

Technological factors include the use of a POS system to increase customer loyalty and optimize business processes; growth in the relevance of online orders (through the Yandex aggregator or the creation of its delivery system); the beginning of the automation of the cooking process (the introduction of robotics for the preparation of drinks/light burgers, etc.).

Based on the results of the PEST analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn. Socio-demographic factors are the most significant for the development of the restaurant market. On the one hand, the growing relevance of online orders for restaurant meals and home deliveries is evident. On the other hand, the phenomenon of “seizing stress”, the development of domestic tourism, and the choice of restaurants as an entertainment option are also notable trends.

Economic and political factors have an ambiguous impact on the restaurant market: as a positive (growth in demand for full-service restaurants, growth in import substitution policies, government support for the business sector); and negative (a decrease in the number of foreign guests, an increase in inflation, a drop in disposable incomes of Russians, an increase in the cost of raw materials and equipment).

Technological factors, such as the use of a POS system, automation using robotics, cooperation with delivery aggregators, or having its delivery, contribute to the development of the restaurant industry if the establishment uses these opportunities and implements innovative solutions in its business processes.

Content analysis of websites of Moscow restaurant business establishments

At the second stage of the study, a content analysis method was employed to examine the websites of Moscow’s restaurant business establishments and identify the primary trends in the Moscow restaurant market. The sample set includes 50 establishments that are popular among visitors, with ratings from 4.5 points according to the Yandex neural network.

The categories of analysis were: type of cuisine, variety of dishes and drinks, use of certain products in cooking, technological innovations, environmental friendliness or adherence to the principles of sustainable development, formats of establishments, quality of service, atmosphere in the hall, convenience of location, availability of additional services, price category.

Based on the analysis results, the main trends observed in the Moscow restaurant market in 2024 were identified.

First, the focus is on expanding gastronomic diversity and developing new culinary traditions. Moscow restaurants offer a diverse range of dishes and drinks from around the world, enabling guests to savor international and regional cuisine without needing to travel outside the city or country. Many restaurants in Moscow are experimenting with new culinary traditions and integrating different styles of cuisine, which is positively perceived by visitors.

Second, preparing healthy food and vegetarian cuisine. With the growing interest in a healthy lifestyle and more conscious eating, Moscow restaurants are actively offering health-oriented dishes to visitors. Vegetarian, vegan, and raw food dishes are becoming popular.

Third, the use of farm products and local ingredients in cooking. Establishments in Moscow focus on using local and organic products, as well as direct deliveries of environmentally friendly products from other regions and countries. This allows you to create more environmentally friendly and tasty dishes.

Fourth, the growing popularity of craft drinks. Craft beer, cocktails, and wines are gaining popularity among visitors to Moscow restaurants, and restaurants are starting to offer a dedicated line of drinks.

Fifth, a focus on a high level of service and a personal approach. Restaurants in Moscow pay special attention to the quality of service, striving to meet the individual needs and requests of each guest.

Sixth, the use of a variety of restaurant formats. In Moscow, you can find restaurants of various formats to satisfy the needs of different consumer segments: from street cafes and fast food establishments to high-end restaurants with distinctive Michelin stars.

Seventh, the popularity of restaurant delivery and takeaway services. With an increase in the number of working-from-home and self-employed citizens, food delivery and the ability to take food with them are becoming increasingly popular services.

Eighth, the introduction of technological innovation. Restaurants are adopting digital technologies to improve the visitor experience. Modern technological innovations include online ordering, electronic menus, and table reservation systems accessed through mobile applications.

Ninth, following the principles of sustainable development and environmental friendliness in the restaurant business model. The restaurant business in Moscow is becoming increasingly focused on the principles of sustainable development and environmental responsibility, as evidenced by a decrease in the use of disposable packaging, optimization and structuring of waste, and a transition to environmentally friendly energy sources.

After analyzing the activities of the best restaurants in Moscow according to the Yandex neural network, we can conclude that the key to the success of the institution is the specialization of the kitchen, the quality of dishes, the use of technological innovations, as well as uniqueness (for example, the presence of its garden at the Twins Garden restaurant on the roof).

Survey of visitors to Moscow restaurants

At the third stage of the study, a survey was conducted among visitors to restaurants and cafes in Moscow. A questionnaire was developed, the blocks of which revealed the features of consumer behavior in the restaurant services market. In February and March 2024, 360 respondents were interviewed, representing a quota of various segments of visitors to Moscow restaurants (according to the typology of G. A. Polynskaya [22]) who visited or ordered delivery from Moscow restaurants.

The survey results highlight the following characteristics of consumer behavior in the restaurant market.

The first feature is the active involvement of the audience in visiting Moscow restaurants, cafes, and bars: every second respondent (52%) notes regular visits to restaurants. The frequency of visiting restaurants varies: almost daily (34%), several times a week (18%), no more than once a week (9%), several times a month (36%), and several times a year (3%).

Notably, not only office workers visit restaurant establishments, but also other categories of people, including the self-employed and freelancers.

The second feature is the focus on ordering dishes from Moscow restaurants and cafes using mobile applications and delivery services. 73% of respondents say that they use these opportunities regularly: almost daily (48%), several times a week (21%), no more than once a week (11%), several times a month (16%), several times a year (4%) (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 Frequency of visits to restaurants and cafes, frequency of use of restaurant food delivery services, %

As a third feature, we note the dominant influence of rational factors when choosing a point of visit: for 29% of respondents, the price factor is of paramount importance; for 24%, convenience of location (near the metro, in the city center, with the ability to park a car, etc.); for 38%, peculiarity of the provided dishes and drinks (variety, certain ingredients in the composition of dishes, the peculiarities of cooking), for 3%, an additional entertainment program and other services in the restaurant (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2 Restaurant selection factors, %

For some respondents, symbolic (irrational) factors are of paramount importance when choosing a restaurant to visit. Specifically, 6% of respondents believe that the image of a restaurant is the most critical factor in deciding whether to see it.

The fourth feature is a change in the structure of consumer motivation when visiting restaurants and cafes. If several years ago the main motives for visiting restaurant business institutions were the celebration of events, leisure activities [23], now respondents most often choose other motives: obtaining gastronomic and different types of pleasure from visiting a restaurant (25%), communicating with friends and colleagues in the framework of official and informal meetings (61%), satisfying the need for food (do not cook dishes yourself) (12%).

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The study's prospects are that understanding the characteristics of consumer behavior will allow restaurateurs to create more personalized offers, taking into account the preferences and habits of visitors. Analysis of consumer behavior will help identify the most popular dishes and drinks, as well as determine the optimal pricing policy. Understanding changes in consumer behavior will enable restaurateurs to adapt more quickly to new trends, such as the rise of online orders, food delivery, the use of mobile applications [24], and other technological solutions [25]. Analysis of consumer behavior will help to develop more effective marketing strategies aimed at attracting and retaining customers. This may include the use of social media, affiliate programs, loyalty, and other tools.

The results of a comprehensive study allow us to formulate the following conclusions.

Firstly, a complex of political, economic, socio-demographic, and technological factors has a diverse impact on the Moscow restaurant market in general, as well as on consumer behavior in particular. Several factors (the spread of import substitution policies, the growing popularity of full-service restaurants, the ever increasing demand for online orders and deliveries of restaurant dishes) have a stimulating effect on the development of the restaurant market; other factors (a decrease in the number of foreign tourists, rising inflation, falling incomes of Russians, an increase in the cost of raw materials and equipment) negatively affect the restaurant market.

Second, the main trends in the Moscow restaurant market are: the orientation of restaurants to prepare healthy meals and vegetarian cuisine; use of farm products and local ingredients in prepared dishes; introduction of technological innovations that simplify consumer experience; focus on sustainability and sustainability in the business model; variety of restaurant formats, dishes and drinks, taking into account the needs of representatives of various segments of consumers; following a high level of service and personal approach to consumers; demand for the delivery of restaurant dishes and takeaway services.

Third, consumer practices in the restaurant market indicate, on the one hand, the active involvement of the audience in visiting restaurants, cafes, and bars in Moscow; on the other hand, the use of restaurant food delivery services through mobile applications and restaurant websites.

Fourth, the dominant influence of rational factors was revealed when consumers choose a restaurant to visit, which indicates consumer awareness in decision-making.

Fifth, a change in the structure of consumer motivation was revealed when visiting restaurants and cafes. The primary needs that underlie the motives for visiting restaurant business institutions are: the need for communication (interacting with friends and colleagues in both formal and informal settings within restaurants), and the need for pleasure (hedonic motive).

As areas of further research corresponding to the subject area, we designate: the study of changes in consumer practices under the influence of the VUCA environment; exploring the impact of digital and standard communication tools on restaurant decision-making; and examining the phenomenon of customers visiting restaurant establishments on a budget.

REFERENCES

1. Konovalova, E. E., Makusheva, O. N., & Timokhovich, A. N. (2023). Prospects for the Development of Advertising Activities in the Tourism and Hospitality Industry. *Bulletin of the Altai Academy of Economics and Law*, (3), 70–74. <https://doi.org/10.17513/vaael.2742> (in Russ.)
2. Neustrueva, A. S. (2023). The Russian Catering Market: Features and Development Trends. *Science Diary*, 2(86), 87–98. (in Russ.)
3. Zaretsky, E. N. (2023). Criteria for Increasing the Competitiveness of the Domestic Restaurant Business. *Fundamentals of Economics, Management and Law*, 2(37), 89–94. https://doi.org/10.51608/23058641_2023_2_89 (in Russ.)
4. Chausov, N. Yu., & Vlasenkov, A. A. (2023). Quality of service at a catering establishment. *Economy and management: problems, solutions*, 7(139), 72–81. <https://doi.org/10.36871/ek.up.p.r.2023.07.02.005> (in Russ.)
5. Lavrova, T. A. (2022). Economic features of restaurant activities in unfavorable market conditions. *Bulletin of the hospitality industry*, 10, 50–53. https://doi.org/10.51608/23058641_2023_2_89 (in Russ.)
6. Fields, R. (2014). Restaurant Success by the Numbers. USA: Ten Speed Press, 320. (in Russ.)
7. Wuyters, B., & Groen, J. (2021). Online influence. How to manage people's behavior so that they make purchases online. *Biblos Publ.*, 448. (in Russ.)
8. Rejeb, A., Abdollahi, A., & Rejeb, K. et al. (2023). Tracing knowledge evolution flows in scholarly restaurant research: a main path analysis. *Qual Quant*, 57, 2183–2209. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11135-022-01440-7>
9. Mohanty, P., Singh, A. M., Hussain, S., & Gavinolla, M. R. (2022). Disrupted Diners: Impacts of COVID-19 on Restaurant Service Systems and Technological Adaptations. In: Hassan, A., Sharma, A., Kennell, J., Mohanty, P. (eds) *Tourism and Hospitality in Asia: Crisis, Resilience and Recovery*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-5763-5_8
10. Karthikeyan, P., Aishwariya Rani, V., Jeyavarshini, B., & Muthupriyaadharshini, M. N. (2023). Sentimental Analysis and Classification of Restaurant Reviews. In: Jacob, I. J., Kolandapalayam Shanmugam, S., Izonin, I. (eds) *Data Intelligence and Cognitive Informatics. Algorithms for Intelligent Systems*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-6004-8_20
11. Boabaid, J., & Marnoto, S. (2023). The Impact of Food Delivery Applications on the Restaurant

- Industry: The Perception of Restaurant Managers in the Metropolitan Area of Porto. In: Reis, J. L., Peter, M. K., Varela González, J. A., Bogdanović, Z. (eds) *Marketing and Smart Technologies. Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies*, vol 337. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-9099-1_53
12. Steur, A. J., Fritzsche, F., & Seiter, M. (2022). It's all about the text: An experimental investigation of inconsistent reviews on restaurant booking platforms. *Electronic Markets*, 32, 1187–1220. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12525-022-00525-3>
 13. Fainshtein, E. (2022). Value Propositions of Restaurant Delivery Systems: A Text Mining-Based Review. In: Beskopylny, A., Shamtsyan, M. (eds) *XIV International Scientific Conference "INTERAGROMASH 2021". Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 246. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-81619-3_54
 14. Zhang, K. S., Chen, C. M., & Chang, W. Y. (2022). A Study on Online Reservation Behavior of Hotel Catering Industry. In: Liu, Q., Liu, X., Cheng, J., Shen, T., Tian, Y. (eds) *Proceedings of the 12th International Conference on Computer Engineering and Networks. CENet 2022. Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering*, vol 961. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-6901-0_108
 15. Banerjee, S., Sen, A., & Zahay, D. (2023). The Effect of In-Store Electronic Word of Mouth on Local Competitor Spillovers in the Quick-Service Restaurant Industry. *Electronic Commerce Research*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10660-023-09742-0>
 16. Fauza, G., Millenia, A. R., Nursiwi, A., Padmaningrum, D., Ariviani, S., & Prasetyo, H. (2023). Applying Importance Performance Analysis (IPA) to Measure the Customer Satisfaction on Food Safety Practices in Restaurant. In: Rosyidi, C. N., Laksono, P. W., Jauhari, W. A., Hisjam, M. (eds) *Proceedings of the 6th Asia Pacific Conference on Manufacturing Systems and 4th International Manufacturing Engineering Conference. iMEC-APCOMS 2022. Lecture Notes in Mechanical Engineering*. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-99-1245-2_28
 17. Ling, E. S. W., Chua, BL., & Han, H. (2023). In search of a reciprocal relationship in dessert cafés: linking customer perceived innovativeness to value co-creation behavior. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10, 897. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-023-02353-y>
 18. Kankam, G. (2023). Service quality and business performance: the mediating role of innovation. *Discover Analytics*, 1, 6. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s44257-023-00006-7>
 19. Kholod, T., & Bellomi, I. J. (2023). "Does Your Restaurant Deliver?" The Change in Consumer Behavior Due to COVID-19 Pandemic in Restaurant Delivery Market: Study of Restaurants in Rome, Italy. In: Demir, E., Bilgin, M. H., Danis, H., D'Ascenzo, F. (eds) *Eurasian Business and Economics Perspectives. EBES 2022. Eurasian Studies in Business and Economics*, vol 26. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-30061-5_10
 20. Akamatsu, R., Tonsho, N., & Saiki, M. et al. (2022). Restaurant managers' readiness to maintain people's healthy weight and minimise food waste in Japan. *BMC Public Health*, 22, 831. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-13274-x>
 21. Bianchi, F., Luick, M., & Bandy, L. et al. (2023). The impact of altering restaurant and menu option position on food selected from an experimental food delivery platform: a randomised controlled trial. *International Journal of Behavioral Nutrition and Physical Activity*, 20, 60. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12966-023-01456-8>
 22. Polynskaya, G. A. (2023). Classification of visitors to traditional restaurants by level of satisfaction: the influence of cognitive and emotional components. *Marketing and marketing research*, 3, 218–229. (in Russ.)
 23. Latyshova, L. S. (2021). Marketing analysis: tools and cases. *Dashkov i K Publ.*, 142. (in Russ.)
 24. Singh, P. R., Nazre Amarnath, T. K., Khurram, M., Tripathi, S., & Chandrasekharan, D. (2023).

Restaurant Automation Through IoT and NLP Techniques. In: Joby, P. P., Balas, V. E., Palanisamy, R. (eds) *IoT Based Control Networks and Intelligent Systems. Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems*, vol 528. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-5845-8_10

25. Campos, F., Lima Santos, L., & Gomes, C. (2023). How to Innovate and Strengthen Management Accounting in a Family Restaurant Business. In: Valeri, M. (eds) *Family Businesses in Tourism and Hospitality. Tourism, Hospitality & Event Management*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-28053-5_9

INFORMATION ABOUT THE AUTHOR

Alexandra N. Timokhovich	Associate Professor, Cand. Sci. (Psychology). Associate Professor of the Department of Advertising and Public Relations. State University of Management. E-mail: an_timokhovich@guu.ru . ORCID ID: 0000-0001-5326-5975	Writing - Review & Editing, Conceptualization, Methodology, Visualization, Investigation
--------------------------	---	--

The author have declared that no competing interests exist

Copyright: © Alexandra N. Timokhovich, 2024

Editor: Andrey B. Kondrashikhin. Academy of Municipal Management (Ukraine)